

I am the Lost Sheep!

However, I am the lost sheep from the 100 sheep that went missing; thus, I was found through diligent seeking by the Lord, Jesus Christ, and brought back into the hands of His Father; He said: I am well pleased because of the marvelous work mine son had done. On the contrary, no more will I go missing or astray from into the hands of Him who has created both Heaven and Earth and Has the authority to give and take away our lives as he pleases without questions! That doesn't mean I won't face trials, tribulations, enticement, etc.

Henceforth, He has promised not to leave nor forsake me through these cold, miserable, daunting, and painful moments by comforting me with His Holy Spirit. I am not independent, for God knows that the adversary, the devil, prowls around like a roaring and hungry lion, seeking someone like me to devour. He has admonished me to be sober-minded, watchful, resist the devil's scheme and remain firm in the measure of faith He has assigned.

The Lord has made me understand that after all these daunting moments that should last for a little while, He who has called me to His eternal life in Christ Jesus, the God of all grace, will himself confirm, strengthen, and establish me! I don't know about you, whether you are lost or not, but what I can tell you, brethren, Jesus Christ is the only way to a life of makeover and righteousness.

Therefore he is willing to comfort you; in the way, he has been comforting me. Let's take heed! I am not ashamed nor afraid to profess my wrongdoings, and you should not? Even the devil is frightened of the aftermath of an unrighteous life after death, and so am I! And that's why Jesus Christ gave Himself as a ransom for the salvation of Humankind. These are my subjective opinions; they are receptive to acceptance or rejection but not an imposition.